

Supporting Information for

Characterization of a consensus-designed trans-cinnamic acid decarboxylase for styrene biosynthesis

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SUPPORTING INFORMATION TEXT

Materials and methods

Analytical ultracentrifugation

An Optima XL-I analytical ultracentrifuge (Beckman-Coulter, Palo Alto, CA) equipped with a UV-visible absorbance detection system was used. Experiments were carried out at 20°C using an AnTi50 rotor, and absorbance measurements were taken at 280 nm. Sedimentation velocity experiments were performed using standard double sector Epon-Charcoal centerpieces (12-mm optical path) at a rotation speed of 48,000 rpm. Sedimentation coefficient distributions were derived by performing direct linear least-squares boundary fitting of the sedimentation velocity profiles using the SEDFIT software(1, 2). SEDNTERP software (3) was used to adjust S values to standard conditions (20°C and water). Apparent weight-average buoyant molecular weights were obtained by fitting a single species model to the experimental data using a MATLAB program based on the conservation of signal algorithm. Protein molecular weights were calculated using a partial specific protein volume of 0.725 cm³/g.

Dynamic light scattering (DLS)

The protein mass was determined using the Svedberg equation, with the sedimentation coefficient (S) obtained by sedimentation rate analysis, and the diffusion coefficient (D) obtained by DLS.

$$M = \frac{RTs}{(1 - \bar{v}\rho)D}$$

T, R, \bar{v} and ρ are the absolute temperature in Kelvin, the universal gas constant, the partial specific volume of the protein (obtained from its sequence) and the density of the buffer, respectively.

Differential scanning fluorimetry (DSF)

Thermal denaturation assays were performed using a MyIQ2 Real-Time PCR instrument (4) as described in supplementary material. A 25 μ L solution of PSC1 at concentrations of 2, 5 and 10 μ M supplemented with 5x SYPRO orange in 50 mM Hepes (pH 7.0) and 150 mM NaCl, was heated from 23°C to 85°C at a rate of 1°C per minute. Fluorescence emission was continuously monitored, and melting temperatures (T_m) were determined using Bio-Rad iQ5 software.

SUPPLEMENTARY FIGURES

Figure S1. Chemical structures of the $\text{prFMN}_{\text{iminium}}$ and $\text{prFMN}_{\text{ketimine}}$ models. Modified from (5).

Figure S2. Schematic overview of the biosynthesis of prFMN in *Pseudomonas putida*. The T1E numbers represent the locus tag in the *P. putida* DOT-T1E genome. Abbreviations: DMAPP, dimethylallyl pyrophosphate; DMAP, dimethylallyl monophosphate; FMN_{ox} , oxidized flavin mononucleotide; FMN_{red} , reduced flavin mononucleotide; prFMN, prenylated FMN.

Figure S3. Electrophoretic separation of purified PSC1. After the SDS-PAGE separation in 12% (w/v) polyacrylamide gel, a band of ~55 kDa was identified.

Figure S4. Sedimentation velocity analytical ultracentrifugation of PSC1. The assays were conducted at 20°C, using an AnTi50 rotor, under the specific conditions described in the Methods section.

Figure S5. Chemical structures of *trans*-cinnamic acid analogues tested as PSC1 substrates.

Figure S6. Schematic representation showing the topology of PSC1, with the three domains of the monomer indicated. α -helices are represented in red while β -strands are represented in green.

A)

B)

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PSC1 MSALNEAERFRPFTQVLRKSGDLLEITTEIDPNLEVQAIDRRVVEKLFHAPLENDRKGA----SKNREILGCGGGLRS 75
sp|A2QHE5|FDC1_ASPNC MSAQPAELCFRSPVEALRQNDLVEINTTIDPNLEAAAIRRVQPTNDWAPLFNNLIGM----KNELESLIGAGGGLRK 75
sp|Q03034|FDC1_YEAST MRKLNEAERFRPFTQVLRKSGDLLEITTEIDPNLEVQAIDRRVVEKLFHAPLENDRKGA----SKNREILGCGGGLRS 75
sp|B9WJ66|FDC1_CANDC -NSLNPAERFRPFTQVLRKSGDLLEITTEIDPNLEVQAIDRRVVEKLFHAPLENDRKQDPEENIDPKRESRILGCGGGLRS 79

PSC1 KKGNDHARLRASHLGLDSQTMMKIIDYLDKAK-TKKIIPFHEVLSAGALQENIISGDEIIDPSLWVLLKHCQGGKYLQ 154
sp|A2QHE5|FDC1_ASPNC SSADRYGRLRASHLGLPTASMEIIDDMISAS-DMPFIEPTIVE--TGRDRENSLDDSEFDLTELHLEKESQGGKYLQ 152
sp|Q03034|FDC1_YEAST KKGNDHARLRASHLGLDQKTTIIEIIDYLDKCK-EKEIIPFIVVSSAKQTHILSEKINLQSLRIRYVLSQGGKYLQ 154
sp|B9WJ66|FDC1_CANDC -FQNDHARLRASHLGLDSQTFMGEIIDFLANRNFRKYLPEVIVLNDQSRHREKHEIKKEQIIDLTELHLEKESQGGKYLQ 158

PSC1 TYGMVLCQPKKSTNMSIARQMVQDKHITGLVNPQHTFVWVAALIRGDRIFKALSGVPPAALLESMPITRGL 234
sp|A2QHE5|FDC1_ASPNC TYGMVLCQSPDGTNMSIARQMVQDKHITGLVNPQHTFVWVAALIRGDRIFKALSGVPPAALLESMPITRGL 231
sp|Q03034|FDC1_YEAST TYGMVLCQPKKSTNMSIARQMVQDKHITGLVNPQHTFVWVAALIRGDRIFKALSGVPPAALLESMPITRGL 234
sp|B9WJ66|FDC1_CANDC TYGMVLCQSPDGTNMSIARQMVQDKHITGLVNPQHTFVWVAALIRGDRIFKALSGVPPAALLESMPITRGL 238

PSC1 PPSIVGCLLGESEIVVVKCTINDLIVPATSSEVLSGQLSISSETGEGFPFGEHMGYVSPGQDPCPLFQVAIYTRMAAL 314
sp|A2QHE5|FDC1_ASPNC PPSIVGCLLGESEIVVVKCTINDLIVPATSSEVLSGQLSISSETGEGFPFGEHMGYVSPGQDPCPLFQVAIYTRMAAL 311
sp|Q03034|FDC1_YEAST PPSIVGCLLGESEIVVVKCTINDLIVPATSSEVLSGQLSISSETGEGFPFGEHMGYVSPGQDPCPLFQVAIYTRMAAL 314
sp|B9WJ66|FDC1_CANDC PPSIVGCLLGESEIVVVKCTINDLIVPATSSEVLSGQLSISSETGEGFPFGEHMGYVSPGQDPCPLFQVAIYTRMAAL 318

PSC1 EYENPELCTDETHITIGSLASPAEQAIAISGQ---PDLQAPFVEAALDNLALRVLEKRIQALRKNPKEFKRVRGRIE 391
sp|A2QHE5|FDC1_ASPNC EYENPELCTDETHITIGSLASPAEQAIAISGQ---PDLQAPFVEAALDNLALRVLEKRIQALRKNPKEFKRVRGRIE 388
sp|Q03034|FDC1_YEAST EYENPELCTDETHITIGSLASPAEQAIAISGQ---PDLQAPFVEAALDNLALRVLEKRIQALRKNPKEFKRVRGRIE 391
sp|B9WJ66|FDC1_CANDC EYENPELCTDETHITIGSLASPAEQAIAISGQ---PDLQAPFVEAALDNLALRVLEKRIQALRKNPKEFKRVRGRIE 398

PSC1 RSEVVG----FIIHCKILVGGDIDIEIPQVIMAVITRHSQGLDLYYRQVKAALAPVYSQSPRINKLGGKVVNCFPF 467
sp|A2QHE5|FDC1_ASPNC RSEVVG----YIIRLVLVGGDIDIEIPQVIMAVITRHSQGLDLYYRQVKAALAPVYSQSPRINKLGGKVVNCFPF 463
sp|Q03034|FDC1_YEAST RSEVVG----FIIHCKILVGGDIDIEIPQVIMAVITRHSQGLDLYYRQVKAALAPVYSQSPRINKLGGKVVNCFPF 467
sp|B9WJ66|FDC1_CANDC RSEVVG----FIIHCKILVGGDIDIEIPQVIMAVITRHSQGLDLYYRQVKAALAPVYSQSPRINKLGGKVVNCFPF 478

PSC1 QQSE-RDQDFVTQFTI-QYSEKRRLLNMGAYGK- 502
sp|A2QHE5|FDC1_ASPNC TQST-TGRNLSAAGFQYFSGDKRRLNMGKNGFSN 500
sp|Q03034|FDC1_YEAST QQSE-RSPNITCFRQGTFRGQVQRNENAKRYGK- 503
sp|B9WJ66|FDC1_CANDC RSTDFPFRVTCSTN-GYFPRKRYKSGDQWKKYK-- 513
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Figure S7. A) Superimposition of one of the two monomers of PSC1 (PDB ID 9GQR) (red) with one monomer of FDC1 from *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* (PDB ID 4S13) (blue), *Candida dubliniensis* (PDB ID 4ZAD) (cyan), and *Aspergillus niger* (PDB ID 7NF3) (gray). **B)** Sequence alignment between PSC1 and FDC1 from *Aspergillus niger* (UniProtKB ID: A2QHE5), *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* (UniProtKB ID: Q03034) and *Candida dubliniensis* (UniProtKB ID: B9WJ66). The overall identity is 52, 77 and 61%, respectively. Identical residues are highlighted in dark gray, while conserved residues are highlighted in light gray.

SUPPLEMENTARY TABLES

Table S1. Percent identity matrix for eight ferulic acid decarboxylases used in the multiple sequence alignment for designing PSC1. The values represent the percentage of sequence identity between each pair of enzymes, including PSC1.

Yeast species	<i>Saccharomyces cerevisiae</i>	<i>Saccharomyces kudriavzevii</i>	<i>Wickerhamomyces anomalus</i>	<i>Wickerhamomyces ciferrii</i>	<i>Debaryomyces hansenii</i>	<i>[Candida] pseudohaemulonis</i>	<i>[Candida] arabinofermentans</i>	<i>Candida dubliniensis</i>	PSC1
<i>Saccharomyces cerevisiae</i>	100	89	68	64	61	61	60	61	77
<i>Saccharomyces kudriavzevii</i>	89	100	67	63	62	63	60	61	78
<i>Wickerhamomyces anomalus</i>	68	67	100	75	64	64	63	61	80
<i>Wickerhamomyces ciferrii</i>	64	63	75	100	59	61	63	61	75
<i>Debaryomyces hansenii</i>	61	62	64	59	100	80	59	63	74
<i>[Candida] pseudohaemulonis</i>	61	63	64	61	80	100	58	62	76
<i>[Candida] arabinofermentans</i>	60	60	63	63	59	58	100	59	73
<i>Candida dubliniensis</i>	61	61	61	61	63	62	59	100	72
PSC1	77	78	80	75	74	76	73	72	100

Table S2. Parameters of the ultracentrifugation sedimentation analysis.

Parameter	PSC1
Peak	94.6%
sw (S)	5.190
Sw (20,w) (S)	5.994
C (mg/mL)	0.3988
% of total	93.487
Coefficient of friction (f/f_0)	1.258
Mw (Da)	104,691
vbar (cm^3/g)	0.744
vbar20 (cm^3/g)	0.744
Hydration (g/g)	0.000
Buffer density (g/cm^3)	1.0141
Relative viscosity (cP)	1.1018
Minimum Mw for compact sphere (Da)	74,202
Stokes Radius (20°C) (nm)	3.95
a/b(oblate)	5.53
a/b(prolate)	5.12

Table S3. Initial consumption rates of *trans*-cinnamic acid at different temperatures. Resting cells of *Pseudomonas putida* CM12-5 (pPSC1) were prepared as described in the Methods section. The concentration of *trans*-cinnamic acid was monitored for 30 min, during which a linear decrease in substrate levels was observed. Data are the mean values and standard deviations from three independent assays.

Temperature (°C)	Initial consumption rate ($\mu\text{mol}/\text{L}\cdot\text{min}$)
18	3.4 ± 0.4
25	4.0 ± 0.3
30	4.6 ± 0.1
37	6.0 ± 0.3
45	10.6 ± 0.7
50	12.8 ± 0.3

Table S4. Strains and plasmids used in this study.

Strain or plasmid	Characteristics	Reference
Strains		
<i>Pseudomonas putida</i>		
CM12-5	DOT-T1E derivative that overproduces L-Phe. Rif ^R , Tol ^R	(6)
<i>Escherichia coli</i>		
DH5 α	Cloning host. F ⁻ <i>endAI hsdRJ7</i> (r _K ⁻ m _K ⁺) <i>supE44 thi-1 λ-recAI gyrA96 relAI deoR Δ(lacZYA-argF)-U169 Φ80dlacZΔM15</i>	(7)
BL21 (DE3)	F ⁻ , <i>ompT, hsdS</i> (r _B ⁻ m _B ⁻), <i>gal, dcm, lon</i>	(8)
Plasmids		
pET28(b)	Expression vector, 6xHIS. Km ^R	Novagen
pET28(b)::PSC1	pET28(b) bearing the ORF PSC1. Km ^R	This work
pPSC1	pSEVA632 derivative carrying <i>pscl</i> gene. Gm ^R	(9)
pPSC1(I189A)	PSC1 bearing the ORF PSC1 with isoleucine at position 189 replaced by alanine. Gm ^R	This work
pPSC1(Q192A)	PSC1 bearing the ORF PSC1 with glutamine at position 192 replaced by alanine. Gm ^R	This work
pPSC1(I330A)	PSC1 bearing the ORF PSC1 with isoleucine at position 330 replaced by alanine. Gm ^R	This work
pPSC1(F397Y)	PSC1 bearing the ORF PSC1 with phenylalanine at position 397 replaced by tyrosine. Gm ^R	This work
pPSC1(I398T)	PSC1 bearing the ORF PSC1 with isoleucine at position 398 replaced by threonine. Gm ^R	This work
pPSC1(F397Y, I398T)	PSC1 bearing the ORF PSC1 with phenylalanine at position 397 replaced by tyrosine and isoleucine at position 398 replaced by threonine. Gm ^R	This work
pPSC1(R175A)	PSC1 bearing the ORF PSC1 with arginine at position 175 replaced by alanine. Gm ^R	This work
pPSC1(R175K)	PSC1 bearing the ORF PSC1 with arginine at position 175 replaced by lysine. Gm ^R	This work
pPSC1(E285A)	PSC1 bearing the ORF PSC1 with glutamic acid at position 285 replaced by alanine. Gm ^R	This work
pPSC1(E285D)	PSC1 bearing the ORF PSC1 with glutamic acid at position 285 replaced by aspartic acid. Gm ^R	This work

Abbreviations: Rif^R, Gm^R, Km^R and Tol^R stand for resistance to rifampicin, gentamycin, kanamycin and toluene, respectively. L-Phe, L-phenylalanine; Tol, toluene.

Rif and Gm were added, when required, to reach a final concentration of 10 μ g/mL, and Km to 25 μ g/mL.

Table S5. Primers used in this study.

Name	Sequence (5'→3')	Description or purpose
C1 Fw(NdeI)	CGCATATGAGCGCCCTGAACCCGG	Construction of pET28(b)::PSC1
C1 Rv(XhoI)	CTCGAGTTACTTATAGCCGTAGGCGCTCC	Construction of pET28(b)::PSC1
C1 Rv1	CTGCGGGTT <u>GGCC</u> ACCAG	Construction of PSC1 (I189A) mutants
C1 Fw1	CTGGT <u>GGCC</u> AACCCGCAG	Construction of PSC1 (I189A) mutants
C1 Rv2	GGATATG <u>CGCC</u> GGGTTGATCA	Construction of PSC1 (Q192A) mutants
C1 Fw2	TGATCAACCCG <u>GCGC</u> CATATCC	Construction of PSC1 (Q192A) mutants
C1 Rv4	CCGCC <u>GCC</u> CAGGGTATG	Construction of PSC1 (I330A) mutants
C1 Fw4	CCTG <u>GCC</u> GGCGGCCTGGTTA	Construction of PSC1 (I330A) mutants
C1 Rv5	TGATCTCGTGGATGAT <u>GTA</u> GCCCAC	Construction of PSC1 (F397Y) mutants
C1 Fw5	GTGGGCT <u>TAC</u> ATCATCCACGAGATCA	Construction of PSC1 (F397Y) mutants
C1 Rv6	TGATCTCGTGGAT <u>GGT</u> GAAAGCCCAC	Construction of PSC1 (I398T) mutants
C1 Fw6	GTGGGCTT <u>CACC</u> ATCCACGA	Construction of PSC1 (I398T) mutants
C1 Rv7	TGATCTCGTGGAT <u>GGTGT</u> AAGCCCAC	Construction of PSC1 (F397Y, I398T) mutants
C1 Fw7	GTGGGCT <u>TACACC</u> ATCCACGAG	Construction of PSC1 (F397Y, I398T) mutants
M13Rv	CAGGAAACAGCTATGAC	Sequencing of cloned fragments in pSEVA632
M13Fw	GTAAAACGACGGCCAGT	Sequencing of cloned fragments in pSEVA632

Nucleotide triplets modified to generate PSC1 mutants are underlined.

SI REFERENCES

1. P. H. Brown, P. Schuck, A new adaptive grid-size algorithm for the simulation of sedimentation velocity profiles in analytical ultracentrifugation. *Comput Phys Commun* **178**, 105–120 (2008).
2. H. Zhao, *et al.*, Accounting for Solvent Signal Offsets in the Analysis of Interferometric Sedimentation Velocity Data. *Macromol Biosci* **10**, 736–745 (2010).
3. J. S. Philo, SEDNTERP: a calculation and database utility to aid interpretation of analytical ultracentrifugation and light scattering data. *European Biophysics Journal* **52**, 233–266 (2023).
4. M. Fernández, *et al.*, Determination of Ligand Profiles for *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* Solute Binding Proteins. *Int J Mol Sci* **20**, 5156 (2019).
5. K. A. P. Payne, *et al.*, New cofactor supports α,β -unsaturated acid decarboxylation via 1,3-dipolar cycloaddition. *Nature* **522**, 497–501 (2015).
6. C. Molina-Santiago, *et al.*, *Pseudomonas putida* as a platform for the synthesis of aromatic compounds. *Microbiology (N Y)* **162**, 1535–1543 (2016).
7. S. G. Grant, J. Jessee, F. R. Bloom, D. Hanahan, Differential plasmid rescue from transgenic mouse DNAs into *Escherichia coli* methylation-restriction mutants. *Proc Natl Acad Sci U S A* **87**, 4645–4649 (1990).
8. F. W. Studier, B. A. Moffatt, Use of Bacteriophage T7 RNA Polymerase to Direct Selective High-level Expression of Cloned Genes. *J Mol Biol* **189**, 113–130 (1986).
9. A. García-Franco, P. Godoy, E. Duque, J. L. Ramos, Engineering styrene biosynthesis: designing a functional trans-cinnamic acid decarboxylase in *Pseudomonas*. *Microb Cell Fact* **23** (2024).